

Chapter 18

Prediction and Mitigation of Wild Forest Fires using AI - Literature review

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Prediction and Mitigation of Wild Forest Fires Using AI - Literature review

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Abstract

Wildfires pose an escalating global threat exacerbated by climate change and human activity, necessitating advanced predictive systems to mitigate ecological and societal impacts. This literature review evaluated 28 studies, from 2020 to 2025, to assess the integration of Business Intelligence & Analytics including Machine Learning and Deep Learning in wildfires prediction, based on PRISMA guidelines to ensure methodological rigor. Key findings highlighted the dominance of Random Forest and Convolutional Neural Networks in spatial-temporal modelling, persistent challenges in data heterogeneity and model interoperability, and a misalignment between academic metrics and operational priorities like early detection. The synthesis underscored the urgent need for interdisciplinary collaboration, lightweight architectures, and the stakeholder-centric frameworks to bridge theoretical advancements with employable solutions in wildfires management.

Keywords: Wildfire prediction, Business Intelligence and Analytics, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Literature Review.

1 Introduction

Wildfires have emerged as a growing global threat, exacerbated by climate change, land mismanagement, and human expansion into fire-prone regions. These disasters cause irreversible ecological damage, economic losses, and pose significant risks to human safety. Traditional wildfire management approaches, often reactive and resource-intensive, are increasingly inadequate in addressing these challenges [28]. The integration of Business Intelligence & Analytics (BI&A) including traditional Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques offers a transformative opportunity for proactive wildfire prediction and mitigation.

This literature review, from 2020 to 2025, in English, evaluated 28 studies to assess the effectiveness of BI&A and ML/DL in wildfire forecasting, focusing on model performance, data quality, and real-world implementation barriers. By synthesizing cutting-edge research, this study aimed to bridge the gap between theoretical advancements and operational deployment, providing actionable insights for researchers, policymakers, and disaster management agencies.

In recent years, the intersection of BI&A with traditional ML and DL has gained increasing traction as a promising avenue for enhancing wildfire prediction and response capabilities [6], [3]. The literature from 2020 to 2025 publication years revealed a significant shift from traditional rule-based and statistical approaches toward data-driven, Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced forecasting models. This transition was largely motivated by the growing availability of heterogeneous data sources—such as satellite imagery, meteorological data, and topographic information—and the advancement of computational resources capable of handling large-scale, high-dimensional datasets.

Furthermore, hybrid and ensemble models combining BI&A with ML/DL frameworks had been explored to enhance predictive reliability and decision-making support. These approaches leveraged the strengths of multiple algorithms and data fusion techniques, offering improved adaptability to diverse geospatial contexts. Several studies had also incorporated real-time data pipelines and geospatial dashboards, facilitating near-instantaneous risk assessments and visualizations that can aid emergency responders and policymakers [4], [12], [27].

Despite these advancements, literature identified persistent challenges. Data quality remained a fundamental issue, especially regarding inconsistencies across spatial and temporal resolutions. Model interpretability, particularly for DL models, was another critical barrier to real-world adoption, as stakeholders often require transparent and explainable outputs. Scalability and generalizability across regions with varying ecological and socio-economic conditions also continued to limit the operational

deployment of AI-driven wildfire management systems. Overall, the current body of research demonstrated considerable potential for the integration of BI&A with ML/DL in wildfire forecasting. However, achieving practical impact necessitates further work on model transparency, cross-domain interoperability, and the incorporation of domain knowledge into algorithmic design.

This literature review addressed 4 research questions (Table 1) to evaluate the BI&A including traditional ML and DL methods in wildfire prediction systems. These questions were used to analyse technical advancements, data ecosystems, performance metrics, and implementation barriers, aiming to bridge gaps between theoretical innovation and operational deployment.

Table 1 - RQ, motivations and connection to fire mitigation

RQ	Motivation	Connection to Fire Mitigation
RQ1: What are the current state-of-the-art BI&A techniques including traditional ML and DL models in wildfire prediction systems?	Identify effective models and their comparative advantages in wildfire contexts	High-accuracy predictions enable optimized resource allocation (e.g., firefighting teams, evacuations)
RQ2: What types of datasets and preprocessing methods are most employed?	Evaluate data quality, sources, and preprocessing challenges	Reliable integration of heterogeneous data improves model generalizability across regions
RQ3: What are the key performance metrics used for evaluating wildfire prediction models?	Assess the alignment of metrics with operational needs	Interpretable metrics foster trust and enable rapid decision-making by agencies
RQ4: What are the major implementation challenges in operational systems?	Highlight barriers like computational costs or cross-regional validation	Scalable, explainable solutions are critical for adoption in diverse ecosystems

The first research question (RQ1) focused on identifying state-of-the-art BI&A techniques including traditional ML and DL models that demonstrate high accuracy in wildfire contexts. Their efficacy in real-time prediction directly supported optimized resource allocation for firefighting and evacuation efforts. RQ2 answer examined datasets and preprocessing methods, analysing the integration of heterogeneous data sources like satellite imagery, IoT sensors, and climate records. Inconsistencies in resolution, format, and quality may hindered model generalizability, underscoring the need for standardized fusion techniques. RQ3 pretended to evaluate performance metrics, investigating if traditional indicators like accuracy failed to align with operational priorities such as early detection rates and false alarm minimization. Fire agencies require interpretable metrics to prioritize actionable insights during emergencies. Finally, RQ4 answer pretended to highlight implementation challenges, including the opacity of "black box" models, computational costs, and validation disparities across ecosystems. Scalability and explainability emerged as critical factors for adoption, particularly in regions with limited resources or diverse environmental conditions. Addressing these challenges requires balancing technical sophistication with practical usability to ensure solutions meet the evolving demands of wildfire mitigation.

In this paper, section 2 describes the methodology used section 3 presents the results obtained from the analysis of the papers, section 4 discusses the results and section 5 gives some conclusions. The final section lists the references used along the paper.

2 Methodology

This section outlines the systematic approach adopted to review recent advancements in BI&A applications for wildfire prediction and mitigation. The methodology was based on Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyzes (PRISMA) guidelines, ensuring rigor and transparency in article selection, quality assessment, and synthesis. Each phase of the review process, planning, execution, and analysis was structured to address the defined research questions (RQs) and validate the practical relevance of the findings.

This review employed a multi-phase screening process (Table 2) to refine an extensive pool of academic

literature into a focused corpus of studies relevant to BI&A-driven wildfire prediction. This structured approach balanced breadth and specificity, ensuring methodological rigor while addressing the rapid evolution of machine learning applications in fire management.

Table 2 - Search string refinement and results

Phase	Search String	Results
Initial Query	("Business Intelligence" OR "BI") AND ("Forest Fire" OR "Wildfire") AND ("Predict" OR "Forecast") AND ("Machine Learning" OR "Deep Learning") AND (Since 2020)	4,680
Title Screening	(intitle:"wildfire" OR intitle:"fire" OR intitle:"forest") AND (intitle:"analytics" OR intitle:"analyses" OR intitle:"analysis" OR intitle:"review" OR intitle:"case study") AND ("Business Intelligence" OR "BI") AND ("Forest Fire" OR "Wildfire") AND ("Predict" OR "Forecast") AND ("Machine Learning" OR "Deep Learning") AND (Since 2020)	77
Abstract Screening	[Abstract review to ensure the quality of inclusion criteria]	28

The initial query combined key terms across four domains, BI&A, wildfire terminology, predictive functions, and technical approaches, yielding 4,680 records. This broad scope captured recent advancements but included substantial noise from unrelated theoretical frameworks or non-technical studies. Title screening applied stringent criteria to the title, requiring explicit mention of analytical methods and wildfire contexts, which reduced results to 77 articles. This phase eliminated studies lacking practical validation, such as general fire science research or policy analyses without BI&A integration. Abstract screening prioritized technical depth and alignment with predefined quality criteria, further narrowing the selection to 28 studies. This final phase excluded articles with insufficient methodological detail, such as those omitting preprocessing steps or validation protocols. The iterative refinement ensured that the retained studies addressed operational challenges, such as data heterogeneity and model scalability, while maintaining relevance to real-world fire mitigation. The process underscored the necessity of systematic filtering to isolate actionable insights within a rapidly expanding research landscape.

The literature review applied predefined quality inclusion criteria (Table 3) to evaluate the methodological rigor and practical relevance of studies integrating BI&A and traditional ML and DL in wildfire prediction. These criteria focused on clarity of research objectives, methodological transparency, data documentation, metric alignment, and acknowledgment of implementation barriers, ensuring studies balanced technical innovation with operational applicability.

Table 3 – Quality Inclusion criteria

Quality Inclusion Criteria
Are the research objectives clearly stated and relevant to wildfire prediction?
Is the proposed methodology well-described?
Are the datasets and preprocessing methods adequately documented?
Are the evaluation metrics appropriate and comprehensively reported?
Are the limitations and practical implementation challenges discussed?

The first criterion assessed whether studies clearly defined objectives tied to wildfire prediction, such as early detection or spread modelling, ensuring alignment with real-world fire management needs. The second evaluated methodological descriptions, emphasizing the need for detailed workflows of BI&A methods including traditional ML algorithms and DL architectures to enable reproducibility. Studies lacking explicit documentation of preprocessing steps or model configurations were flagged, as incomplete methodologies hinder validation and scalability. The remaining criteria addressed data transparency and practical limitations. Adequate dataset documentation, including sources like satellite imagery or climate records, was critical to assess model generalizability across ecosystems. Similarly, comprehensive reporting of evaluation metrics ensured alignment with operational priorities, such as minimizing false alarms or latency in detection systems. Finally, discussions of limitations, such as

computational costs or regional validation gaps, were essential to contextualize findings and guide future improvements. Together, these criteria ensured the reviewed studies provided actionable insights while highlighting persistent challenges in translating theoretical models into deployable solutions. The literature review followed a structured selection process based on PRISMA guidelines, as illustrated in the flow diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - PRISMA diagram

This methodology ensured transparency and rigor in identifying relevant studies at the intersection of BI&A for wildfire prediction, balancing comprehensive coverage with methodological relevance. The initial search across academic databases aggregated via Google Scholar yielded 4,680 records, reflecting broad interest in predictive analytics for fire management. Sources included peer-reviewed platforms such as IEEE, MDPI, and ScienceDirect, alongside repositories like ResearchGate. Title screening applied strict criteria, requiring explicit mention of analytical methods and wildfire contexts, reducing the pool to 77 studies. This phase eliminated 4,603 records, primarily theoretical ML papers, non-technical policy analyses, or studies lacking BI&A integration. Abstract screening further refined the corpus to 29 articles by prioritizing technical validation, dataset documentation, and alignment with predefined quality criteria. The final selection retained studies that addressed operational challenges such as data heterogeneity, model interpretability, and scalability. The annual distribution of publications highlighted a growing emphasis on BI&A-driven wildfire research, with a notable concentration of studies from 2023 onward. This trend underscores the accelerating adoption of advanced analytics to address escalating environmental threats.

The annual distribution of publications (Figure 2) revealed evolving research priorities in BI&A with machine learning applications for wildfire prediction, with notable fluctuations in output between 2020 and 2025.

Figure 2 - Year-wise distribution of publications (2020–2023)

The distribution of articles across digital libraries highlights the diverse academic sources contributing to wildfire prediction research, reflecting varying publication practices and accessibility within the field. Peer-reviewed platforms such as IEEE and ScienceDirect collectively account for six articles, representing foundational technical frameworks and validation studies. MDPI contribute with five articles, emphasizing open-access trends and interdisciplinary collaboration in environmental analytics.

3 Results

This section synthesizes perspectives from the literature review, addressing state-of-the-art techniques, design considerations, and evaluation frameworks for BI&A driven wildfire prediction models.

The following analysis synthesizes the capabilities and limitations of prominent wildfire prediction models (Table 4), emphasizing their technical strengths, operational constraints, and alignment with real-world fire mitigation needs.

This evaluation focused on six computational approaches widely applied in wildfire research, highlighting their adaptability to environmental challenges and scalability in diverse ecosystems.

Table 4 - Analysis of wildfire prediction models

Model	Strengths	Weaknesses	References
Binary Logistic Regression (BLR)	Interpretable risk probability; low computational cost.	Limited to linear relationships; requires feature engineering.	[5], [12]
Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)	High precision in fire/smoke detection via satellite imagery.	Performance degrades under fog/smoke; requires labelled image data.	[4], [6], [8], [21], [20]
Digital Twin Systems	Integrates real-time satellite/sensor data; enables scenario testing.	High computational/resource demands; require calibration.	[11], [12]
Hidden Markov Models (HMM)	Model's probabilistic transitions; interpretable.	Limited to annual predictions; ignores spatial factors.	[14], [12]
Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)	Captures temporal dependencies in weather/fire data; ideal for seasonal risk.	Requires large datasets; computationally intensive for real-time deployment.	[13], [16], [17]
Random Forest (RF)	Handles heterogeneous data; quantifies feature importance.	Less effective for temporal predictions; risk of overfitting.	[3], [5], [19], [26]

BLR was valued for its interpretability and computational efficiency, making it suitable for initial risk assessments in resource-limited regions. However, its reliance on linear relationships and manual feature engineering restricts its utility in modelling complex, non-linear fire dynamics. CNNs excelled in detecting fires and smoke through high-resolution satellite imagery, achieving precision in spatial analysis. Challenges emerged under adverse conditions such as fog or smoke, where image quality deteriorates, and the dependency on labelled datasets complicate scalability. Digital Twin Systems integrated real-time data streams from satellites and sensors, enabling dynamic fire spread simulations. Their operational adoption was hindered by significant computational costs and the need for frequent calibration, particularly in regions with limited technical infrastructure. HMMs offered probabilistic insights into temporal fire transitions but overlooked spatial factors, limiting their application to annual risk forecasts rather than real-time predictions. LSTM networks effectively captured temporal dependencies in weather and fire data, ideal for seasonal risk modelling. Their reliance on extensive datasets and computational resources posed barriers to real-time deployment in areas with sparse historical records. RF handled heterogeneous data effectively, providing feature importance metrics for actionable insights. While robust for static predictions, it struggled with temporal sequences and risks overfitting without rigorous parameter tuning. The models' strengths and weaknesses reflected broader tensions between technical sophistication and practical usability. For instance, while CNNs and LSTMs advanced predictive accuracy, their resource demands highlighted the need for lightweight alternatives in operational settings. Similarly, Digital Twin Systems and RF models demonstrated the potential of integrating diverse data sources but underscored the importance of balancing complexity with deplorability. These insights aligned with current research priorities, which emphasized adaptable frameworks capable of addressing escalating wildfire threats while accommodating ecological and operational diversity. The literature review identified three primary data categories critical to wildfire prediction systems (Table 5), each with distinct sources, limitations, and implications for model reliability. These datasets, satellite imagery, weather data, and historical fire records formed the foundation of predictive analytics but faced challenges that affected their utility in diverse operational contexts.

Table 5 - Wildfire dataset landscape

Dataset Type	Sources	Limitations	References
Satellite Imagery	NASA FIRMS, MODIS	Low resolution, cloud obstruction	[3], [5], [8], [11], [18], [19], [20], [26], [27]
Weather Data	ERA5, NOAA	Temporal gaps, coarse spatial scales	[16], [23]
Historical Fire Records	Global Fire Atlas, CALFIRE	Biased toward populated regions	[3], [5], [6], [8], [11], [15], [18], [19], [23], [27]

Satellite imagery from NASA FIRMS and MODIS enabled broad spatial coverage for fire detection, yet low resolution and frequent cloud obstruction compromise precision in dynamic environments. Efforts to address these limitations focused on integrating auxiliary data sources, such as UAV imagery, to enhance resolution and filled observational gaps during adverse conditions. Weather data from ERA5 and NOAA provided essential climatic variables but suffered from temporal discontinuities and coarse spatial granularity, complicating localized fire spread modelling. Advanced downscaling techniques and ML interpolation were increasingly employed to refine spatial resolution and mitigate temporal inconsistencies. Historical fire records from Global Fire Atlas and CALFIRE offered valuable insights into fire behaviour but exhibited geographic biases, overrepresenting populated or monitored regions, while neglecting remote ecosystems. This skew distorted risk assessments and hindered model generalizability across diverse landscapes. Recent methodologies emphasized transfer learning and synthetic data generation to counteract biases, improving predictive accuracy in underrepresented areas. These advancements highlighted the ongoing need to balance data availability with ecological representativeness, ensuring wildfire models remain adaptable to the escalating variability of fire-prone environments.

The analysis of the frequency of the use of preprocessing techniques revealed their varying adoption across wildfire prediction studies, reflecting priorities in addressing data quality challenges. Feature selection was

utilized in 18 articles to reduce dimensionality and enhance model efficiency, while train-test splitting appeared in 20 studies to ensure robust validation. Outlier handling, though less prevalent, remained essential for minimizing noise in heterogeneous datasets. The predominance of missing data handling aligned with the challenges of integrating incomplete satellite or weather records, where imputation or exclusion strategies were vital for maintaining prediction reliability. Feature selection's prominence highlighted the need to balance computational complexity with actionable insights, particularly when processing multi-source data like satellite imagery and climate variables. Train-test splitting's widespread use emphasized the field's focus on reproducibility, though its application often overlooked temporal or spatial dependencies unique to wildfire dynamics. Outlier handling, while less prioritized, addressed anomalies arising from sensor errors or extreme weather events, which could distort risk assessments. The distribution of these techniques illustrated the iterative nature of data refinement in wildfire prediction, where preprocessing choices directly influenced model accuracy and operational trust. As data heterogeneity grows, standardized protocols for these methods will become increasingly critical to ensure consistency across diverse ecosystems and fire regimes.

The evaluation metrics employed in wildfire prediction research demonstrated a strong emphasis on comprehensive performance assessment, with Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under the Curve (ROC-AUC) emerging as the most widely reported indicator, utilized in 24 studies. This preference reflected its ability to balance sensitivity and specificity, critical for models operating in imbalanced fire/no-fire scenarios. Precision, Recall, and F1-score followed closely, appearing in 22, 21, and 23 studies respectively, highlighting the field's dual focus on minimizing false alarms and maximizing early detection rates. ROC-AUC's dominance underscored its suitability for evaluating models tasked with prioritizing high-risk areas amid data imbalances, a common challenge in wildfire datasets. Precision's prevalence aligned with operational demands to reduce false positives, ensuring resource allocation is not diverted by erroneous alerts. Recall's slightly lower adoption might indicate gaps in addressing early detection needs, as maximizing true positive rates remained vital for timely evacuations and pre-emptive containment. The F1-score's intermediate position bridged these priorities, offering a balanced measure for stakeholders requiring both accuracy and reliability. These trends revealed a consensus on the importance of multi-metric evaluation but also highlighted potential mismatches between academic benchmarks and operational realities. For instance, while ROC-AUC provided theoretical robustness, fire agencies often prioritized latency-adjusted metrics absent from standardized reporting. The distribution underscored the need for domain-specific evaluation frameworks that aligned technical performance with actionable outcomes, ensuring predictive models met the urgent, evolving demands of wildfire management.

4 Discussion

The literature review revealed persistent barriers to deploying robust wildfire prediction systems, while identifying opportunities for advancing BI&A applications in fire management. This review identified persistent challenges and future priorities for advancing wildfire prediction systems and were categorized as seen in Table 6. These categories reflected the multifaceted nature of developing reliable, scalable solutions capable of addressing escalating fire risks amid ecological and operational complexities.

Dataset characteristics faced limitations in geographical and temporal coverage, often focusing on specific regions or short-term records, which restricted model generalizability. Future efforts emphasize collecting multi-year, multi-region data to capture diverse fire regimes and integrating socioeconomic variables like land use patterns, which were frequently excluded despite their influence on fire susceptibility. Preprocessing challenges centred on noisy or incomplete sensor data, driving the need for automated cleaning pipelines to streamline data refinement. Severe class imbalances between fire and non-fire instances further complicated model training, prompting exploration of synthetic data generation to enhance representation of rare but critical fire events. Model selection grappled with accuracy compute trade-offs, particularly for hybrid architectures like CNN-LSTM networks, which struggled with real-time deployment due to high resource demands. Regularization techniques and ensemble methods were prioritized to improve robustness in data-scarce environments. Interpretability remained a critical barrier, as opaque "black box" models hinder trust among firefighters and policymakers. Hybrid systems combining rule-based logic with AI, alongside model distillation for transparency, were proposed to bridge this gap. The lack of widespread adoption of explainability tools like SHAP or LIME underscored the urgency of developing intuitive interfaces that aligned technical outputs with operational decision-making. These insights charted a path toward adaptive frameworks that balanced

innovation with practicality, ensuring predictive systems evolved in tandem with ecological dynamics and stakeholder needs. By addressing data biases, computational constraints, and transparency gaps, the field can transition from theoretical excellence to operational resilience, empowering communities to anticipate and mitigate wildfire threats proactively.

Table 6 - Challenges and future directions in wildfire prediction

Category	Challenges	Future Directions
Dataset Characteristics	Limited geographical/temporal coverage	Collect multi-region, multi-year data
	Exclusion of human activity/land use factors	Integrate socioeconomic variables
Pre-Processing	Noisy/missing sensor data	Develop automated cleaning pipelines
	Severe class imbalance (fire vs. non-fire)	Synthetic data generation
Model Selection	Accuracy-compute trade-offs (e.g., LSTM/CNN hybrids)	Regularization techniques for small datasets
	No consensus on optimal architecture	Ensemble methods for robustness
Interpretability	Black-box neural networks hinder stakeholder trust	Hybrid rule-based + AI systems
	Lack of SHAP/LIME adoption in reviewed studies	Model distillation for transparency

5 Conclusion

The integration of BI&A with traditional ML and DL techniques had undeniably revolutionized wildfire prediction capabilities, offering unprecedented accuracy in risk assessment and early detection. The review synthesized key findings across four research questions (Table 7), offering a comprehensive assessment of advancements and persistent gaps in wildfire prediction systems.

Table 7 - Key findings across Research Questions

RQ	Answer
RQ1: What are the current state-of-the-art BI&A techniques including traditional ML and DL models in wildfire prediction systems?	RF and CNNs dominated due to their efficacy in handling spatial-temporal data and heterogeneous inputs.
RQ2: What types of datasets and preprocessing methods are most employed?	Satellite imagery (NASA FIRMS, MODIS), weather data (ERA5, NOAA), and historical fire records were primary sources.
RQ3: What are the key performance metrics for evaluating wildfire prediction models?	ROC-AUC and F1-score were most prevalent, balancing sensitivity and specificity.
RQ4: What are the major implementation challenges in operational systems?	Key barriers included "black box" model opacity, high computational costs for real-time deployment, and cross-regional validation failures.

The dominance of RF and CNNs in wildfire prediction underscored their adaptability to spatial-temporal data and heterogeneous inputs, such as satellite imagery and multi-source environmental variables. Hybrid architecture, including CNN-LSTM models, demonstrated potential for capturing both spatial and temporal fire dynamics but faced scalability challenges due to computational intensity. While deep learning models achieved high accuracy, their "black box" nature and resource demands hindered real-world adoption, particularly in resource-constrained regions.

Satellite imagery from NASA FIRMS and MODIS, alongside weather data from ERA5 and NOAA, formed the backbone of wildfire datasets, supplemented by historical fire records. However,

preprocessing these datasets remained a critical hurdle, with missing data imputation and feature selection prioritized to address gaps and noise. Spatial-temporal splitting methods were increasingly adopted to validate models across diverse ecosystems, though resolution mismatches and geographic biases persisted, limiting generalizability.

Performance metrics like ROC-AUC and F1-score dominated academic evaluations, balancing Sensitivity and Specificity in fire/no-fire classification. However, operational priorities such as early detection rates (Recall) and false alarm minimization remained underrepresented, revealing a disconnection between technical benchmarks and frontline needs. This gap emphasized the necessity for domain-specific metrics that align with evacuation timelines and resource allocation protocols.

Implementation challenges were centred on translating theoretical models into deployable tools. The opacity of complex neural networks eroded stakeholder trust, while high computational costs restricted real-time deployment of advanced architectures. Cross-regional validation failures further exposed limitations in model adaptability, as algorithms trained on specific ecosystems often underperformed in geographically distinct areas. Addressing these barriers requires integrating socioeconomic variables, such as land use patterns and human activity, into datasets, alongside hybrid systems that combine AI with rule-based logic for interpretability. Scalable cloud-edge architectures and model distillation techniques emerged as critical enablers for balancing accuracy with operational feasibility.

These conclusions collectively advocate for interdisciplinary frameworks that prioritize not only technological innovation but also ecological representativeness, computational efficiency, and stakeholder collaboration. By harmonizing data quality, model transparency, and evaluation rigor, the field can advance toward predictive systems capable of mitigating wildfire risks in an era of escalating environmental uncertainty.

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